

*Students motivation to study and how the transformation to distance learning disrupts the process of learning : A case study in a local university of Brunei.
(Reflective Critique Report)*

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1. First reflection

I became interested in discovering this topic when I struggled with distance learning myself as a student during the COVID-19 restrictions were still critical. However the motivation I have planned towards my future career has driven me to overcome these challenges and by focusing on the delegated tasks given by lecturers, I was able to carry myself properly. Musa and Idris (2020) stated in their studies that Bruneians culture norms aspires towards a prestigious job for their future. I find that motivation comes with interesting driven factors that exist and catalyses the behavior of all human beings. Robbins and Judge (2014) described in their textbook upon the subject of motivation as one of the ways to approach an individual and make them become efficient. In a self-perspective, it is more into how an individual encourages themselves in completing something that can give them benefit in the present or/and the future. Hence my interest as a student is to uncover what motivates university students to study in accordance to two types of motivation which are self-efficacy and self-determination theory. Aside from motivation, I would maintain distance learning as the main topic of my report.

Aside from just motivation, I would also investigate what are the roles of lecturers towards students, whether they are also included in motivating students or lecturers are just a facilitator to deliver the studies and knowledge towards students. Ahmad and Safaria (2013) described that lecturers can influence students in making them achieve a bigger goal and challenge themselves. Therefore in other words, an interpersonal relationship is created between lecturers and students when the student develops an external advantage such as support, feedbacks that could be used to enhance their will to study. However these are just theories and studies done in other countries it could be different in Brunei, which intrigues me to do a research upon.

Brunei universities had recently undergone the transformation to adapting distance learning due to COVID-19. Although universities in Brunei equip technological applications such as file sharing and online tests, the use of web conferences has not been fully utilized as all lectures were mainly delivered physically. Therefore, I would like to investigate whether the use of distance learning has affected the process of learning despite the usual provision of lecture materials such as notes and lectures.

Ethical factors to be considered in my research is primarily on the eligibility of data being used for the report while abiding by the COVID-19 social distancing. The data for the report requires a detailed answer from individuals which opted towards interviewing the participants. However with the limitations of physical interaction and time management for the assignment, the sample would be focusing on a small-group of participants. Time management was also delayed due to the ethical policy mandated by University of Brunei Darussalam needing to be completed before conducting my research. Otherwise the report would be ineligible and invalid to proceed.

2. Interim reflection

2.1. Sources used for the research

After the first draft has been sent, my supervisor advised me to narrow my research in focusing more on the range of sources from year 2000-2020 that are related to my research. I have found numerous studies that touched on the implications of distance learning. The research sources I have used are mainly from TandF online, researchgate, sprinkler link and organisational behaviour textbook by Robbins and Judge (2014). The secondary references I took are mainly in favour of my research which could come across as a biased opinion in any case I did not come across more articles that were against my research. It was challenging to acquire some secondary research as I do not have access to the articles. However I managed to acquire them by using the university's Wi-Fi which was a hassle as I have to travel back and forth to the university just to get access to some articles.

In order to continue my progress of the report, I noticed in all the secondary research I have compiled, includes a conceptual framework that showcases a clear direction to where the report is heading. However the research I have progressed at the time was still complex as I have to link the theory of motivation to the theory of distance learning. Also the research questions were still in question such as whether I should link the literature review based on distance learning during COVID-19 or distance learning in general. It was also challenging to relate how distance learning affects student's motivation in terms of their goal-setting theory because despite the challenges students face during their education timeline, their goal would remain unchanged. This issue had me thinking that in order for me to discover how distance learning affects student's motivation, I could inquire participants on their CGPA before and after COVID-19. This strategy would be challenging as it would require participants to disclose what could be a sensitive matter and for me to inquire about their CGPA, I would have to wait for the end of their semester and time limitations is one of the main issues I have to manage.

2.2. Challenges faced in relation to theories

Assessing through the articles, I could not find much information regarding the connection of self-determination and self-efficacy theory. Between searching for articles that concluded both self-determination with self-efficacy as a motivation for students and a limit set for the article date publication (2000-2020) the timeline of research was exceedingly consumed. Apparently I discovered most articles associate self-efficacy with goal-setting theory as motivations to study. My progress was further hindered when I accidentally included goal-setting theory as one of the questions for the interview which I only came across after all the participants completed the interview. In order to save time, I overcame this issue by changing my first hypothesis (connecting self-determination and self-efficacy) into a new hypothesis (connecting self-efficacy with goal setting theory). These two theories are chosen because Bandura (1994) mentioned self-efficacy and goal-setting theory interlinked with one another in fostering an individual's motivation. As a result, I have to rearrange my hypothesis and the theories I have progressed so far by removing whichever theories in my report that touched on self-determination.

2.3. Challenges faced in relation to using terms

In addition to the challenges I faced regarding theories, I was also confused with the term “interrelationship” and “interpersonal relationship” to depict the relationship between lecturers and students in the development of students academic progress. While composing my research I kept on interchanging between those terms which I thought carries the same meaning. However, thinking of consistency for the report, I found out the term “interrelationship” was not present in the textbook of my module of which I have used as the main reference for the research. As a solution, I decided to refer to the term “interpersonal relationship” in the report as a description of the relationship between students and lecturer.

In relation to the research questions, my initial plan was to come up with three questions; *1) Is there a difference in the academic progress between distance learning and traditional learning? 2) Does having interrelationship with lecturers result in; Self efficacy? Self determination? 3) Would distance learning still be effective if it were not for the pandemic?.* Nonetheless as the research progressed, the findings from the interviews provided more insights on the type of motivations students kept to further their studies and the importance of interpersonal relationships with lecturers for their academic advancement during and before COVID-19 restrictions. Hence I decided to come up with 6 research questions that focused on the implications of distance learning; *RQ1 Does distance learning disrupt the student process of learning? RQ2 Does distance learning affect students' engagement with lecturer? RQ3 Are students interested in distance learning if the pandemic did not occur?;* and motivation to study; *RQ 1 Do students set a high goal setting theory as a motivation? RQ 2 Are goal-setting theory and self-efficacy relatable in an educational perspective? RQ 3 Can goal-setting theory be influenced by lecturers?* By using division of the research questions, it gives me a clear instruction on how to construct my analysis and relate it to the literature review. Provided with these research questions, I also was able to draw the conceptual framework that can help in understanding my report further.

2.4. Challenges during collection of data

Creating the interview questions on motivation were mainly sourced from reading the organisational behaviour textbook. I took some time to read and understand the theories used in my report then construct the questions myself according to my understanding. Whereas the questions for distance learning and interpersonal relationship were based on articles I have read and I also observed my surroundings such as struggles faced by my friends with distance learning. I made sure that the questions were simple and understandable by students on Degree level. Participants chosen are from the student councils batch 2019/20, Universiti Islam Sultan Sharif Ali. I approached one of the student councils and inquired if they are interested in participating for an interview. In the beginning they were reluctant as they thought it required a physical meeting for the interview. However after consulting with my lecturer, the interview could be done online. Hence this provides me an advantage by using Whatsapp to get the data. Despite the ease of access to the interview questions, getting the participant response was still challenging; perhaps they were reluctant to give their private information such as phone

numbers. Eventually I managed to get responses by changing the interview into an open-ended question on Google form.

In the context of analysing the findings, I experienced a struggle in dividing the responses as open-ended questions provided different answers from each participant. Despite this issue however, I reviewed some of the articles I have used and some of the research used a generalizing method by dividing responses by the type of behaviour. On that account, drawing from the samples of articles, I generalized the responses based on the common word they used and how they interpret the answers into several characters. For instance, one of the interview questions includes “what are your thoughts on the positive and negative impact towards distance learning”, most of the answers involve ease of comfort and ability to study comfortably which I generalised as “convenience”. An intriguing finding I have discovered that correlates with a study by Muiz and Idris (2014) is the most common characteristics of the young population in Brunei aspires to a luxury life and a well-paid job. In addition to these characteristics, most students in my findings aimed to make their parents proud by completing their degree with flying colours.

3. Final reflection

As I completed my findings and discussion I was able to rephrase my title. I initially titled my research as “*The implications of distance learning (DL) and interrelationship communication towards academic motivation: A case study in Brunei*” which highlights the importance of lecturers and communication in helping students progress using distance learning amidst the pandemic. However after consulting with my supervisor, she advised me to reword my title and confusion upon the interchanging of terms between “interrelationship” and “interpersonal relationship” in my report has led me to reconstruct the title to “*Students motivation to study and how the transformation to distance learning disrupts the process of learning : A case study in a local university of Brunei*”. As I have initially planned from the beginning, I would like to highlight the implications of distance learning and student’s motivation but after analysing the findings, it concluded to a deeper hypothesis on the type of motivation students create for themselves.

I was also able to answer my research questions based on the findings I have collected and analysed. I think this is only possible because I used relevant questions based on the theories I was focusing on. It was comforting knowing that the findings were able to answer the research questions I have intended. Overall what I find to be the most crucial part in making a report is to have a timeline set in advance that can help in any case of modification needed for the report. I have also learned that initial plans were supposed to be used as a guidance in structuring the research and as it progresses, modifications should be carried out to strengthen the quality of the research. When dealing with restructuring the flow of the report, I learned that referring to some articles will not only strengthen the hypothesis made in a report but it also assists in the direction of where the report should focus on, creating research questions and analysis of findings. By looking through some articles, I have discovered the importance of research questions and conceptual framework in depicting a clear picture to where the report is heading.

In conclusion I was only able to follow about 70% of my initial plan because changes were required in order to keep the consistency and quality of the report. I noticed that most changes were initiated once the findings were collected. Surprisingly after analysing findings, I was brought upon with new ideas such as changing a few terms and coming up with a few new research questions. I am glad to have succeeded in answering my hypothesis while maintaining the focus of the report despite the changes made. Throughout the report I was able to discover certain qualities such as time management and research methodologies. However I forgot to set contingency plans in case any of the initial plans were disrupted which had caused a delay in the progression of my report. Hence in the future, I will consider creating contingency plans and research some articles in advance to ease the progress of creating research.

Reference

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